

GENERALIZED LORENTZ TRANSFORMATIONS

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This article presents the generalized Lorentz transformations of time, space, velocity and acceleration which can be applied in any inertial or non-inertial (non-rotating) frame.

Introduction

If we consider a (non-rotating) frame S relative to another inertial frame Σ then the time (t), the position (\mathbf{r}), the velocity (\mathbf{v}) and the acceleration (\mathbf{a}) of a (massive or non-massive) particle relative to the frame Σ are given by:

$$t = \int_0^t \gamma dt + \gamma \frac{\vec{r} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi}}{c^2} + h$$

$$\mathbf{r} = \vec{r} + \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma + 1} \frac{(\vec{r} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \boldsymbol{\varphi}}{c^2} + \int_0^t \gamma \boldsymbol{\varphi} dt + \mathbf{k}$$

$$\mathbf{v} \doteq \frac{d\mathbf{r}}{dt}$$

$$\mathbf{a} \doteq \frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt}$$

where (t, \vec{r}) are the time and the position of the particle relative to the frame S ($\boldsymbol{\mu}, \boldsymbol{\varphi}, \boldsymbol{\alpha}$) are the position, the velocity and the acceleration of the origin of the frame S relative to the frame Σ , ($\vec{\mu}$) is the position of the origin of the frame Σ relative to the frame S, (h, \mathbf{k}) are constant between the frames Σ & S (c) is the speed of light in vacuum, and $\gamma \doteq (1 - \boldsymbol{\varphi} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi} / c^2)^{-1/2}$

- $\frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \frac{1}{c^2} = \frac{\gamma-1}{\varphi^2} \quad (\varphi^2 \doteq \boldsymbol{\varphi} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi})$
- $\vec{r} + \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \frac{(\vec{r} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \boldsymbol{\varphi}}{c^2} = \gamma \vec{r} + \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \frac{(\vec{r} \times \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \times \boldsymbol{\varphi}}{c^2}$
- $\vec{\mu} + \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \frac{(\vec{\mu} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \boldsymbol{\varphi}}{c^2} = \gamma \vec{\mu} + \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \frac{(\vec{\mu} \times \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \times \boldsymbol{\varphi}}{c^2}$
- $\boldsymbol{\mu} = \int_0^t \gamma \boldsymbol{\varphi} dt + \mathbf{k} = \int_0^t \boldsymbol{\varphi} dt + \mathbf{k} = -\vec{\mu} - \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \frac{(\vec{\mu} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \boldsymbol{\varphi}}{c^2}$

The frame S is inertial when ($\boldsymbol{\alpha} = 0$)

The frame S is non-inertial (rectilinear accelerated motion) when ($\boldsymbol{\alpha} \neq 0$) and ($\boldsymbol{\alpha} \times \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$)

The frame S is non-inertial (uniform circular motion) when ($\boldsymbol{\alpha} \neq 0$) and ($\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$)

If the frame S is inertial then the observer S must use a fixed origin O such that ($\vec{\mu} \times \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$)

If the frame S is non-inertial (rectilinear accelerated motion) then the observer S must use a fixed origin O such that ($\vec{\mu} \times \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$)

If the frame S is non-inertial (uniform circular motion) then the observer S must use a fixed origin O such that ($\vec{\mu} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$)

If the frame S is inertial then ($\boldsymbol{\alpha} = 0$), ($\boldsymbol{\varphi} = \text{constant}$), ($\gamma = \text{constant}$) ($\int_0^t \gamma dt = \gamma t$), ($\boldsymbol{\mu} = \gamma \boldsymbol{\varphi} t + \mathbf{k}$) and ($\vec{\mu} \times \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$)

If the frame S is non-inertial (rectilinear accelerated motion) then ($\boldsymbol{\alpha} \neq 0$) ($\boldsymbol{\alpha} \times \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$) and ($\vec{\mu} \times \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$)

If the frame S is non-inertial (uniform circular motion) then ($\boldsymbol{\alpha} \neq 0$) ($\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$), ($\gamma = \text{constant}$), ($\int_0^t \gamma dt = \gamma t$) and ($\vec{\mu} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$)

If the frame S is inertial or non-inertial (non-rotating) then the observer S can use test particles such that ($\vec{r} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$) or ($\vec{r} \times \boldsymbol{\varphi} = 0$)

General Observations

It is known that in inertial frames the local geometry is Euclidean and that in non-inertial frames the local geometry is in general non-Euclidean.

According to this article, the local line element of the frame S must be obtained from the local line element of the frame Σ .

Therefore, the local line element (in rectilinear coordinates) in the frame Σ and the local line element in the frame S are given by:

$$ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - d\mathbf{r}^2$$

$$ds^2 = \left[\left(1 + \frac{\mathbf{w} \cdot \vec{r}}{c^2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\phi} \times \vec{r}}{c} \right)^2 \right] c^2 dt^2 - 2 \left(\boldsymbol{\phi} \times \vec{r} \right) d\vec{r} dt - d\vec{r}^2$$

$$\mathbf{w} \doteq \gamma^2 \left(\boldsymbol{\alpha} + \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma + 1} \frac{(\boldsymbol{\alpha} \cdot \boldsymbol{\varphi}) \boldsymbol{\varphi}}{c^2} \right) \quad , \quad \boldsymbol{\phi} \doteq \gamma^1 \left(\frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma + 1} \frac{(\boldsymbol{\varphi} \times \boldsymbol{\alpha})}{c^2} \right)$$

According to this article, the kinematic quantities ($t, \mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{a}$) are the proper kinematic quantities of the frame Σ .

Therefore, the kinematic quantity (t) is a tensor of rank 0 and the kinematic quantities ($\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{a}$) are tensors of rank 1.

Finally, the velocity of light in vacuum is (\mathbf{c}) in the frame Σ and (\vec{c}) in the frame S and ($\mathbf{c} \cdot \mathbf{c}$) & ($\vec{c} \cdot \vec{c}$) are constant in the frames Σ & S.

Bibliography

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